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The Relationship between The Job Characteristics of the Teaching Profession and School Effectiveness*

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ABSTRACT

When teachers' autonomy, roles and responsibilities, the importance given to the teaching profession, teacher competencies and the feedback provided to the teacher are increased, it will contribute to school effectiveness. However, when one of the job characteristics of the teaching profession is insufficient, it is seen that schools become ineffective. In this context, the purpose of this study is to find out the relationship between the job characteristics of the teaching profession and school effectiveness according to the opinions of teachers working at primary and secondary schools. The participants of the study were 376 teachers and the School Effectiveness Scale and the Teaching Profession Job Characteristics Scale were used. The perceptions of the teachers showed that there is strong relation between the job characteristics of teaching profession and school effectiveness.

Keywords: School effectiveness, job characteristics, teaching autonomy

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Introduction

Education is an essential way to convey to students the knowledge and skills necessary to contribute to the development of a country in every sense (Loyce and Victor, 2017). A school is effective as long as it achieves its goals. The main purpose of any change in educational institutions is receiving a better, more qualified, and more effective education. This inevitably results in the emergence of the concept of an effective school. The origin of effective school research is some schools' being more successful than others (Çakır and Kesme, 2018). The concept of an effective school has become an essential topic in the United States since the "Coleman Report" was published in the mid-1960s (Edmonds 1979). The Coleman report and other research findings are disappointing and mean that no matter what education professionals and education administrators do, they cannot increase school success (Balçı, 2011). According to Macbeath and Mortimore (2001) the concept of school effectiveness emerged due to inequalities in society and education, so a movement entitled education for all began. In order to be recognized as effective, schools need to constantly criticize and review their performance. Schools that are continually improving achieve the trust of the society. Çubukçu and Girmen (2006) pointed out that as a result of the studies carried out to provide better quality education in schools, the concept of effective school has emerged. Actually, some schools are described as successful and some as unsuccessful has actually been a factor in the emergence of the concept of effective school.

Considering the previous studies, the most prominent factor and common idea in determining whether a school is effective and successful is student success. One of the criteria that allows to comment on the success graph of students in Turkey is the evaluations applied at the international level. In terms of the skills required in these evaluation studies, the competencies of students in Turkey are below the average competencies demonstrated by their peers living in OECD countries (EARGED, 2010). In recent years, the schools have been increasingly ineffective in Turkey and cannot achieve their goals. There have been increase in students' failure in national and international large-scale exams and the current education system has been unable to provide students with sufficient competencies, so these have led to the intensification of efforts to restructure the education system (ERG, 2012)

The important finding that emerged in the evaluations is that Turkey has the biggest difference between schools in PISA applications among all countries participating in the 2003 implementation. It has been observed that there are differences in achievement even between the same type of schools in the same region in Turkey (Berberoğlu and Kalender, 2005). When we look at Turkey's success in international exams, it is obvious that schools have not reached to be effective schools. From this point of view, schools try to be more successful both at the international and national level (Uğurlu and Demir, 2016).

The school that can't achieve its goals at the expected level is defective in being effective. It is thought that schools in Turkey are becoming increasingly ineffective and cannot meet the expectations of the society. The mistakes made in the orientation of the students in the primary education process negatively affects the secondary education life. The inadequacies in schools and the fact that families think more about the economic dimension while directing them to professions cause problems (Eskicumalı, 2001).

Zigarelli (1996) expresses the effective school characteristics contributing to student success as the quality of the teacher, the participation and satisfaction of the students in school

activities, the presence of a leader school administrator with positive relationships and communication skills, the strong school culture, and the participation of the family. The aim of an effective school is to achieve success with excellent methods. The excellence of the school can be ensured by a healthy school culture and climate as well as the quality of education and training of the teacher (Balçı, 2013). As Balçı (1988) stated; each of the effective school these variables cannot create an effective school alone; it shouldn't be forgotten that these variables can only make a difference when they are together.

The quality of public schools in Turkey has been declining and the most frequently mentioned problems are the ineffectiveness of education and training in schools and the distance from meeting the expectations of students, the environment, parents and the business world (Arslan, Kuru and Saticı, 2010). The ability of schools to respond to the changing needs of society can only be possible by renewing policies and practices. Since schools are the dynamic stones that keep society alive, schools should be effective, constantly improved and strengthened so that they can continuously fulfill their duties (Cafoğlu, 1996). As Polat (2017) stated, there are very few studies on the job characteristics of the teaching profession in Turkey. It is considered that this is due to the fact that the determinant of the framework of education is the state, and what is required for the development of the teaching profession is expected from the state and therefore the need is not felt. Considering the results of the research in general, taking the necessary precautions to prevent the negative effects and determining the antecedent variables was the starting point of this study. In this context, it has been considered important to determine the role of the job characteristics of the teaching profession on school effectiveness, including the importance of teachers' profession, teachers' perceptions of autonomy, their awareness of their roles and responsibilities, receiving appropriate feedback, and their perceptions of their competencies.

Literature Review

Barnard (1968) defines effectiveness as the degree of success of the goals set in cooperation and the work done to achieve these goals.

School Effectiveness

The concept of organizational effectiveness is defined as the ability of an organization to reach inputs, adopt these resources, and eventually reach its goals (Federman, 2006). According to Georgopoulos (1957), the concept of effectiveness in organizations is sometimes defined as success and sometimes as value, and generally focuses on how well an organization does its job and its overall success. As Cameron (1981) pointed out, when conducting research on organizational effectiveness, it should be considered that each effectiveness model is different from each other, one is not superior to the other, and that these models are complementary to each other

The concept of an effective school has become an essential topic in the United States since the "Coleman Report" was published in the mid-1960s (Edmonds 1979). An effective school is a modern and qualified school that adopts the belief that all students can learn and develop (Oral,2005). Mortimore (1993) defined effective school as a school where students developed more than desired from the date they started school, and thus effective schools drew attention with what they brought to students. According to Edmonds (1979), an effective school is a school where every student can learn, attaches importance to equality and quality, offers equal rights to every student, provides a safe working environment for students, and where

students develop continuously. Lezotte (2001) pointed out that the features of effective schools are participation of the family, positive school climate, aiming to provide students with basic skills, prioritizing student development, effective teaching plans and practices.

There are certain characteristics of effective schools in the literature, Şişman (2013) lists these characteristics as follows: school administrator, teacher, student, school program and education-teaching process, school culture and environment, school environment and parents. In an effective school, the headmaster has leadership characteristics and shares the school's goals with teachers, students and parents. At the same time, he understands and emphasizes the qualities of the teaching activity. Obviously, the role of the school principal is very important in terms of school effectiveness (Lezotte, 2001). An effective teacher is a requirement of an effective school. The communication between the teacher and student is always at the heart of education. As long as the quality of the teacher is high, the improvement of the educational effectiveness in the target brings success. It is not possible to plan and create an effective school without an effective teacher (Akan, 2007). The basic principle in effective schools is the belief that every student can learn. In an effective school, the necessary time and support is always provided for each student (Lezotte, 1991). Curriculum in effective schools is prepared in line with the objectives known to the students. Curriculum features of effective schools interact with other features of the system. The teaching practices of schools affect each other and create the states of being effective or ineffective (Brookover, 1982). An effective school interacts with the environment where it receives its input and outputs of school. The effectiveness of a school is related to its harmony with the environment (Yiğit and Bayrakdar, 2006). As Balcı (1988) stated; each of the effective school variables could not create an effective school alone; it shouldn't be forgotten that these variables could only make a difference when they were together.

Job Characteristics of Teaching Profession

Job Characteristics theory was developed by Hackman and Oldham (1974) to explain how much employees were affected by job enrichment and enlargement programs. It is one of the theories that best explains the job characteristics, satisfaction, and motivation of employees (Bilgiç, 2008). If it is necessary to adapt the job characteristics of the teaching profession according to the job characteristics model of Oldham and Hackman, it is possible to list the job characteristics of the teaching profession as follows; Teaching Competencies, Teaching Roles and Responsibilities, The Importance of the Teaching Profession, Teaching Autonomy and Teaching Performance Feedback (Polat, 2017).

The subjects emphasized as teacher competence in the literature are generally the pedagogical abilities of the teachers, such as their relationships with the students, following the student's learning process, communication with parents and the environment, knowledge of the curriculum, working in collaboration with colleagues, and problem-solving skills (Runco, 2003). Teaching competency has a great role in the efficient learning process of students and contributes to their development in learning. At the same time, it shows the level of expertise of teachers in their fields and its effect on their performance (Hakim, 2015).

Teachers have many roles and responsibilities inside and outside of the school. The teacher is the best supporter of the students by allowing them to share and apply their ideas after a lecture in the classroom, observing them and then giving feedback. The teacher facilitates learning, that is, enables students to learn by exploring with the necessary methods, techniques and materials. (Harrison and Killion, 2007). In addition to fulfilling all kinds of responsibilities related to their profession, teachers are expected to make an effort for their own professional

development. Although teaching comes at the beginning of the teacher's duties, the teacher must continue to learn for himself and to adapt to the innovative order (Chaplain, 2008).

Teachers are the most important elements of the structure of an education and have a direct effect on the education system (Adib, 2017). The teacher is at the center of the education system. The greater the importance given to the progress of a society in social, cultural, economic, political and technological fields, the greater the importance that should be given to the teachers who provide them (Day, 2002).

Autonomy is related to how free the employees feel while preparing their work schedule, determining the tools and equipment they will use, deciding on the ways and methods to be followed, and during the working process (Brief and Aldag, 2015). Autonomy, as perceived by teachers, is limited to issues such as the choice of teaching methods and techniques, the selection of resources and materials, in other words, in the classroom, but it is seen as autonomy when teachers are based on collaborative work while making decisions with the school administration on issues such as curriculum and program preparation (Willner, 1990).

Hunter (2006) defined feedback as an employee's being informed clearly and directly about his/her performance. Teachers, like students, need regular, positive, and constructive feedback in order to acquire new positive behaviors. The positive effect of the feedback provided to teachers is seen not only in teacher but also in student achievement. (Scheeler, Ruhl and McAfee, 2004). According to Neary (2000), Teachers are generally aware of the importance of feedback, and they respect constructive criticism, because they feel precious and try to improve their deficiencies.

Purpose and Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to determine the relationships between teachers' perceptions of teaching profession job characteristics and school effectiveness. Within the scope of this purpose, we sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the level of the job characteristics of teaching profession and school effectiveness according to teacher perceptions?
2. Is there any significant relation between the job characteristics of the teaching profession and school effectiveness?
3. Do the job characteristics of the teaching profession predict school effectiveness?

Method

Research Model

In this study, the relationship between teachers' job characteristics and school effectiveness leadership was described. This study was designed in the descriptive relational survey design. Within this scope, the data collected from primary and secondary school teachers were analyzed with quantitative techniques.

Study Group

This research was conducted with teachers working in public primary and secondary schools in province of Uşak in Turkey. According to the data taken from the Uşak Provincial Education Directorate, 1962 primary and secondary school teachers are working in 2020-2021 school year. The population of 1962 is represented by 322 teachers with an error rate of 5%

(Krejcie and Morgan, 1970). Participants were determined by convenient sampling method from the city center. After all, we obtained 376 scales from different schools that were completely filled out.

Data Collection Tools

The School Effectiveness Index was used in this research was developed by Hoy (2009) and rearranged by Demirkasimoğlu and Taşkın (2015) for measuring teachers' perceptions of school effectiveness. Teachers' views on the job characteristics of teaching profession was measured by the Job Characteristics of Teaching Profession scale developed by Polat and Özdemir (2018). Psychometric properties of the relevant scales are explained below.

The school effectiveness scale: The teachers' views on school effectiveness were identified by School Effectiveness Index consisting of thirty-two items. developed by Hoy (2009) and adapted by Demirkasimoğlu and Taşkın (2015), was used to determine the teachers' perception of organizational effectiveness.

In the adaptation study, the scale was tested by confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). The goodness of fit index were reported as [$\chi^2 = 44.07$; $df = 20$; $\chi^2/df = 2.20$ 3.82; GFI = .91; AGFI = .85; RMSEA = .10; CFI = .99; NFI = .97]. Reliability studies of the scale showed that the Cronbach Alpha coefficients is.92. As a result of the validity and reliability studies, it was determined that the 32-item and 4-factor scale was a useful tool for Turkish culture (Demirkasimoğlu and Taşkın, 2015). We also tested the validity of the scale with CFA for our sample. The goodness of fit index results were: [$\chi^2 = 61.26$; $df = 16$; $\chi^2/df = 3.82$; GFI = .96; AGFI = .76; RMSEA = .08; CFI = .98; NFI = .98]. For the reliability analysis of the scale, we calculated the Cronbach Alpha coefficients, the result is as follow: .88. As a result, it is concluded that the School Effectiveness Scale is a valid and reliable tool that could be used in this study when compared with the ideal values in the literature (Kline, 2011) and considered all values as a whole.

The job characteristics of teaching profession scale: The Job Characteristics of Teaching Profession perceptions of teachers were determined by The Job Characteristics of Teaching Profession Scale consisting of 35 items and five dimensions (Teaching Competencies, Teaching Roles and Responsibilities, The Importance of the Teaching Profession, Teaching Autonomy, Teaching Performance Feedback) developed by Polat and Özdemir (2018). According to the results of Explanatory Factor Analysis, total variance was found as %53.823. In the adaptation study, the five-factor structure of the scale was tested by confirmatory factor analysis (CFA [$\chi^2 = 44.07$; $df = 20$; $\chi^2/df = 2.20$ 3.82; GFI = .91; AGFI = .71; RMSEA = .073; CFI = .90; NFI = .75].]. Reliability studies of the scale showed that the Cronbach Alpha coefficients are .89 for Teaching Competencies, .88 for Teaching Roles and Responsibilities, .79 for The Importance of the Teaching Profession, .82 for Teaching Autonomy, .71 for Teaching Performance Feedback. As a result of the validity and reliability studies, it was determined that the 35-item and 5-factor scale was a useful tool Polat and Özdemir (2018). We also tested the validity of the scale with CFA for our sample. The goodness of fit index results were reported as: [$\chi^2 = 1369.27$; $df = 515$; $\chi^2/df = 2.66$; GFI = .82; AGFI = .82; RMSEA = .07; CFI = .94; NFI = .91].]. For the reliability analysis of the scale, we calculated the Cronbach Alpha coefficients are: [.87 for Teaching Competencies, .77 for Teaching Roles and Responsibilities, .60 for The Importance of the Teaching Profession, .82 for Teaching Autonomy, .72 for Teaching Performance Feedback]. As a result, it is concluded that the The Job Characteristics of Teaching

Profession Scale is a valid and reliable tool that could be used in this study when compared with the ideal values in the literature (Kline, 2011) and considered all values as a whole.

Analysis of Data

This research was carried out with teachers working in primary and secondary state schools in Uşak. Because primary schools and secondary schools show similar characteristics, the teachers in these schools were determined as the study group, and in this sense, the application of this study in high schools was also mentioned in the suggestions part of this paper. Necessary legal permissions were obtained from the Uşak Provincial Directorate of National Education. The data collection process of the study was carried out with 376 teachers working in primary and secondary state schools in the province in the 2020-2021 academic year. The data collection process of the study was carried out with 376 teachers working in primary and secondary schools. The data collection was gathered online and on a voluntary basis because of Covid-19 pandemic conditions. Filling the scales took about 5-10 minutes.

Before starting to analyse, missing data and extreme value analyses were done. In addition, the normality tests were conducted, and parametric tests were used. We started main analysis after the preliminary analyzes were completed.

In the study, Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated to determine the relationships between variables. While interpreting the correlation coefficients; an absolute value between 0.70-1.00 is high; a correlation between 0.70 and 0.30 was interpreted as a medium level, and between 0.30 and 0.00 as a low-level relationship (Büyüköztürk, 2007). Hierarchical Regression Analysis was used to determine whether job characteristics are predictive of school effectiveness.

Ethics committee approval

This research was carried out in accordance with the decision of Uşak University Educational Research Ethics Committee dated 12.02.2021 and numbered 2021/13.

Results

In line with our purpose, we first identified descriptive statistics for The Job Characteristics of Teaching Profession and School Effectiveness. Primary and Secondary Schools' teachers arithmetic means and standard deviation scores for these two variables.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of teachers on job characteristics of teaching profession and school effectiveness

	N	\bar{X}	sd
Job Charteristics of Teaching Proffession	376	4,48	,36068
Teaching Competencies	376	4,87	,26016
Teaching Roles and Responsibilities	376	4,41	,62630
The Importance of the Teaching Profession	376	4,74	,41083
Teaching Autonomy	376	3,96	,74060
Teaching Performance Feedback	376	4,46	,54756
School Effectiveness	376	3,77	,75603

In Table 1, the views of primary and secondary school teachers show that the perceptions of teachers from the job characteristics of teaching profession mostly “at a high level” in all five

sub-dimensions. The general mean obtained from the teaching profession job characteristics scale was (\bar{X} :4.48). According to results of the analysis, the mean score for Teaching Competencies is (4,87), for Teaching Roles and Responsibilities is (4,41), for The Importance of the Teaching Profession is (4,74), for Teaching Autonomy is (3,96), for Teaching Performance Feedback is (4,46). It can be said that the general mean and the means of the sub-dimensions obtained from the teaching profession job characteristics scale are generally quite high, except for the teaching autonomy sub-dimension. When the means of the sub-dimensions of job characteristics of the teaching profession are examined, it is seen that the highest mean is in the teaching competencies sub-dimension, while the lowest mean is in the teaching autonomy sub-dimension. The mean obtained from the school effectiveness index according to teacher perceptions was determined as (\bar{X} =3.77). According to the mean score obtained, it can be said that teachers' perceptions of school effectiveness are at a high level.

In the study, multiple correlation analysis was performed to determine the relationship between variables. In this context, the correlation coefficients between these variables are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. The relationship between the job characteristics of the teaching profession and school effectiveness (Pearson Moment Correlation Analysis) (N:376)

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Job Characteristics of Teaching Prof. (1)	1	,636**	,723**	,574**	,780**	,682**	,407**
Teaching Competencies (2)		1	,494**	,520**	,193**	,395**	,159**
Teaching Roles and Responsibilities (3)			1	,373**	,283**	,378**	,262**
The Importance of the Teaching Prof. (4)				1	,244**	,388**	,202**
Teaching Autonomy (5)					1	,449**	,364**
Teaching Performance Feedback (6)						1	,356**
School Effectiveness (7)							1

* Correlations are significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Correlation coefficients between the Job Characteristics of Teaching Profession and School Effectiveness showed that there are positive correlations between these variables. According to this, there is a positive and moderate correlation between the Characteristics of Teaching Profession and School Effectiveness ($r=,407$, $p<.01$). The correlation coefficients between the general scores of the teaching profession job characteristics scale and the perception levels of school effectiveness, from highest to lowest, are teaching autonomy ($r=,364$), teaching profession feedback ($r=,356$), the teaching roles and responsibilities ($r=,262$), the teaching profession importance ($r=,202$) and the teacher competency ($r=,159$). The dimension of job characteristics of the teaching profession, which has the highest correlation coefficient with school effectiveness, is the dimension of teacher autonomy. In accordance with the purpose of the research, hierarchical regression analysis was performed to determine the role of teaching profession job characteristics on school effectiveness and presented in Table 3.

Table 3. The hierarchical regression analysis results regarding the predicting of school effectiveness by job characteristics sub-dimensions of the teaching profession

Predictive variables	School Effectiveness									
	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3		Model 4		Model 5	
	β	t	β	t	β	t	β	t	β	T
Model 1										
Teaching Autonomy	0,364	7,568*	0,256	4,885*	0,240	4,551*	0,239	4,515*	0,236	4,448*
Model 2										
Teaching Performance Feedback			0,240	4,576*	0,204	3,730*	0,197	3,482*	0,205	3,584*
Model 3										
Teaching Roles&Responsibility					0,117	2,294*	0,110	2,083*	0,127	2,265*
Model 4										
Importance of Teaching Profession							0,027	0,509	0,046	0,808
Model 5										
Teaching Competencies									-0,054	-0,901
R ²	0,133		0,179		0,190		0,191		0,193	
ΔR^2	0,133		0,046		0,011		0,001		0,002	
F	57,272*		40,635*		29,153*		21,886		17,662	
* <i>p</i> <.001										

Table 3 shows hierarchical regression analysis regarding the sub-dimensions of job characteristics of the teaching profession predict school effectiveness. It is seen that the predictive level of the dependent variable of the final structure with 5 models is statistically significant and the independent variables explain 19.3% of the total variance in the dependent variable ($F=17.662$; $p<.001$). When we analyze the models one by one the Teaching Autonomy, Teaching Performance Feedback, Teaching Roles&Responsibility are significant predictors of school effectiveness. In this context, teaching autonomy explains %13,3, Teaching Performance Feedback explains %4,6 and Teaching Roles and Responsibilities explains %1,1. Importance of Teaching Profession and Teaching Competencies are not significant predictors of school effectiveness.

Discussion

In this study, the job characteristics of teaching profession and school effectiveness were described and the relation between them were examined according to the perceptions of teachers. Our findings show that when the mean scores of the job characteristics of the teaching profession are examined, it is seen that the highest mean scores are the teaching competencies and importance of teaching profession sub-dimension, while the lowest mean scores are in the teaching autonomy, teaching performance feedback and teaching roles and responsibilities sub-dimension. Polat (2017) reached the similar results in terms of mean scores of sub-dimensions of job characteristics of teaching profession and stated while the teachers feel themselves competent, they don't feel themselves autonomous.

Considering the results of our research, the sub-dimension with the highest mean of the job characteristics of teaching profession is *teaching competence*. Mc Clelland (1998) stated that competence was the basis of a person's success or failure in business life in a given situation. According to other studies on teaching competency, characteristics such as content knowledge, research skills, curriculum dominance, positive attitude to lifelong learning, social competence, communication skills, empathy ability, and following science and technology are accepted as general teacher competencies (Hannon, 2009). In this context, it can be said that teachers generally have pedagogical content knowledge and the required skills of the teaching profession.

The other sub-dimension with the highest mean score when compared with other sub-dimensions is *the importance of teaching profession*. The status of the teaching profession is a frequently discussed issue all over the world. The generally accepted understanding that determines the status of a profession is income and prestige. When we look at the literature, prestige comes to the fore more and two different perspectives have been identified. The first is the respect shown by the society to the teacher and the other is the perception of the profession of the teachers. Regardless of income, the fact that the principle of dignity attracts more attention in research also reflects the importance of teachers in terms of society (Fwu and Wang, 2002). Thus, teachers think that the status and income of teaching profession are low (Ulutaş,2017). Although the perception of teaching profession is low in Turkey, it is possible to say that the importance that the teachers give their profession is high. The reason of this may be related to the nature of teaching profession that requires emotional labour.

Considering the mean scores in our research the lowest mean scores are in the teaching autonomy, *teaching performance feedback* and teaching roles and responsibilities sub-dimension. In the literature, there are many studies on teaching autonomy in Turkey and abroad. Turkey is one of the countries that provides the least autonomy to schools in terms of curriculum, evaluation of students and use of resources among OECD countries. Schools or teachers in

Turkey were not given rights to speak in the determination of the courses, the creation of the course contents and the selection of the course books. Teachers' autonomy behaviors differ significantly in terms of teaching process autonomy and curriculum autonomy according to the branch variable. It is seen that the teachers want more authority and freedom to adapt their lessons according to students (Garvin, 2007; OECD,2011; Öztürk, 2012; Pearson&Hall, 1993; Strong, 2012). Teachers feel that their limited level of autonomy causes the teaching profession to lose its prestige, and they express their sadness (Özaslan, 2015). One of the conclusions we can reach based on previous research is that the curriculum and course content come first in cases that teachers do not feel autonomous. It is a questionable subject how the teachers not feeling autonomous can contribute to school effectiveness. The second questionable subject is that the teachers are given more responsibilities, they need to have more say in the educational processes and act autonomously.

The other sub-dimension which has a lowest mean is *teaching performance feedback*. According to the national TALIS report, Turkey has a young teacher population. Most of the teachers participating in the study are under the age of forty. Teachers stated that they were generally evaluated by school principals and that as a result of their evaluation, there were no feedbacks such as financial reward, increase in salary or changes that could make the profession more attractive, such as advancement in the profession (TALIS,2010). The feedbacks that teachers receive make them highly motivated, work more willingly and diligently, and make them feel valued, but it is not possible to say that teachers can contribute to the effectiveness of the school if they don't get feedback. The ability of schools to respond to the changing needs of society can only be possible by renewing policies and practices. Since schools are the dynamic stones that keep society alive, schools should be made effective, constantly improved, and strengthened so that they can continuously fulfill their duties (Cafoğlu, 1996). As a result, it can be said that the teaching performance feedback is very important in terms of increasing and supporting the teachers' performances.

The other lowest mean of the job characteristics of teaching profession sub-dimension is *teaching roles and responsibilities*. Similarly, of Meriç and Erdem (2000) found that the level of perception of the teaching role and responsibilities is low compared to the other dimensions. According to Eurydice's report (2008), with the increase in social needs, expectations from schools have also increased, which has led to a significant change in the teaching profession in recent years. Especially in the last two decades, the responsibilities given to teachers have increased. This situation may make the teachers think not to fulfill their roles and responsibilities completely and effectively.

In our research, the correlation coefficients between the general scores of the teaching profession job characteristics scale and the perception levels of school effectiveness, from highest to lowest, are teaching autonomy, teaching performance feedback, the teaching roles and responsibilities, the importance of teaching profession and teacher competency. In addition, when considering the predicting level of school effectiveness of the sub-dimensions of the teaching profession job characteristics from highest to lowest, we found the same results. Meriç and Erdem (2000) found that teaching competencies, teaching autonomy and teacher performance feedback sub-dimensions are significant predictors of self-sacrificing work, while teacher roles and responsibilities and the importance of teaching profession sub-dimensions are not significant predictors of self-sacrificing work. In another study, it was determined that autonomy and feedback sub-dimensions significantly predict teachers' enjoyment of work (Mavi,

2015). For this reason, it can be said that the characteristics of teaching profession play important role on variables about teacher performance.

According to our findings, *teaching autonomy* has the highest relation with school effectiveness. In addition, it is the strongest predictor variable of school effectiveness. Teachers should be given full authority in order to increase the quality of education in terms of the right of teachers to plan their own methods, choose their materials according to the needs and characteristics of their students, and to apply them in the classroom in line with their own decisions (Eurydice 2008). From this point of view, it is possible to say that when the autonomy fields of teachers increase, their performances increase, and they use their own potentials more effectively. Furthermore, with the increase of teaching performance the increase of school effectiveness may be expected. In other words, high school effectiveness may be thought as the natural result of teachers' being autonomous in their profession.

According to our study the second important role on school effectiveness belongs to *the teaching performance feedback*. Daryanto (2014) stated that, as in other professions, the capacity of the teacher should be constantly increased with feedback to suit the most up-to-date conditions and the needs of the stakeholders, thus making them proud as an educator. Furthermore, Can (2006) emphasized that developing the teachers' leadership and giving feedback about their development were among the most important roles of school leader. In such a clear school environment, it is expected that the teachers demonstrate more strategic and goal-oriented behaviours. Thanks to the feedbacks from school principals, it can be said that these behaviours have a great role on increasing the school effectiveness.

We found that the third important sub-dimension on school effectiveness was teaching roles and responsibilities. According to Harrison and Killion (2007), teachers have many roles and responsibilities inside and outside the school. After a lecture in the classroom, the teacher allows students to share and apply their ideas, observe them and then give feedback, the teacher facilitates learning and provides the necessary resources. The teacher is an expert, is aware of the curriculum, is a mentor and the teacher is a student who never gives up on learning and development. In this context Sünbül (1996) stated that an effective teaching process depended on how the teachers fulfilled their roles and responsibilities and how they used their potentials. From this perspective, it can be thought that the fulfilling their roles and responsibilities plays important roles on school effectiveness

According to our findings, the sub-dimensions of *teaching competency and the importance of teaching profession* have the lowest relations with school effectiveness. In addition to this, both of the variables aren't significant predictors of school effectiveness. According to Moghtadaie & Taji (2018) in literature *teaching competency* includes knowledge, skills, and attitudes. Blandford (2003) mentioned that teachers see their schools as a learning center and as a matter of teaching profession the teachers improve and develop the quality of education. As these teaching competencies and the importance of teaching profession are already in the nature of teaching profession, they are not being predictors of school effectiveness can be accepted normally.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In this study, the relationship between the job characteristics of the teaching profession and school effectiveness was discussed. In this context, it was concluded that there was an important and high relationship between the job characteristics of the teaching profession and

school effectiveness. Especially, the sub-dimensions of the teaching autonomy, teaching performance feedback and the roles and responsibilities of teaching play important role on school effectiveness.

It is possible to say that the most important characteristics of the teaching profession are teaching autonomy, teaching performance feedback and the roles and responsibilities of teaching. According to the results of the research, in order to increase the effectiveness of the school, autonomy should be provided especially in cases where teachers do not feel autonomous. In addition, it is necessary to provide the feedback they need so that they can continue their profession more willingly and efficiently. Also, a system can be developed where each teacher can express his/her opinion in situations such as creating curriculum and course content where teachers feel the least autonomous. In order to strengthen the autonomy of teachers, it should be provided to the teachers to take part in the process of political decisions at the school and country level. In addition to this, it is necessary to provide supporting them for their own professional development, as they are expected not to give up learning in order to adapt to the required skills of innovative school life.

This research was carried out in primary and secondary schools. In this context, this study may be conducted with different education levels. On the other hand, based on the results of this research, more detailed studies can be studied on the subjects of teaching autonomy, teaching performance feedback and teaching roles and responsibilities. By taking into consideration the importance of school effectiveness different variables on which develop the school effectiveness may be studied.

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